

Water vapour adsorption by L-amino acids at different water activities[†]

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Abstract : Experimental studies on the hydration of all 20 L-amino acids by isopiestic vapour pressure method have been carried out in detail. The water vapour adsorption curves of these amino acids resemble type II or type III BET isotherms. The maximum water uptake (Δn_1^0) of the amino acids at relative humidity equal to unity and values of secondary hydration (n_2^0) of these amino acids at p/p_0 equal to 0.92 have been compared critically with each other. Values of Δn_1^0 and n_2^0 for each amino acid has been found to be different from that of the corresponding amino acid residue obtained from our earlier studies. It appears that many amino acids having hydrophobic side chain may form crystals with strong ionic bonds so that they resist hydration at 0.92 relative humidity. The standard free energies of hydration of all amino acids at p/p_0 equal to unity have been evaluated using the Bull equation. The activity coefficients of several amino acids having low solubilities at p/p_0 close to unity has been evaluated when hydrated mixtures remain in gel state.

Keywords : L-Amino acids, adsorption, polypeptides, thermodynamic parameters, hydration of amino acids.

Introduction

The role of interaction of water with proteins and polypeptides in relation to their stability and biological functions have been reported earlier by many workers¹⁻⁶. In order to understand hydration behaviour of proteins and polypeptides, studies of interaction of water to individual amino acids are very much essential. Amino acids have been classified as "hydrophobic" and "hydrophilic" based on their relative solubilities in water⁷⁻¹⁰. Considerable work has been done on solubilities of amino acids in water and in various solvents at different temperatures¹¹⁻¹⁴. The solubility data have been used to calculate the activity coefficients of amino acids^{14,15}. Both solubility and activity coefficient were found to depend on the length of the carbon chain and dipolar distance of amino acid molecule.

Recently, the extents of hydration of different poly amino acids and their side chain residues^{16,17} in the absence and presence of inorganic salts have been estimated using isopiestic vapour pressure method. Also, the extents of lowering of the boundary tension of different amino acids at air-water, heptane-water, benzene-water

and nitrobenzene-water interfaces^{19,20} have been measured extensively and useful thermodynamic parameters and hydrophobicity scales of the amino acids for these systems have been critically compared. In the present paper using isopiestic vapor pressure technique, attempts will be made to evaluate many thermodynamic parameters related to water-amino acid interaction and the results will be compared with those obtained earlier for corresponding amino acid residues¹⁶ present in the polypeptide chains of 20 different poly amino acids.

Results and discussion

Naturally occurring polypeptides and proteins of various types result from the linear polymerization of twenty different L-amino acids. These amino acids are differentiated by twenty different side-chain groups (vide Fig. 1A). The side-chain groups^{20,21} of alanine, valine, leucine, isoleucine, proline, phenyl alanine, tryptophan, methionine are hydrophobic and nonionic in nature. R groups of glycine, serine, threonine, cystine, tyrosine, asparagine, glutamine residues respectively each contain one nonionic hydrophilic group so that these groups are able to bind water molecules at the hydrophilic site. Besides these,

[†]Dedicated to Professor Suresh C. Ameta on his 60th birthday.

there are five amino acid residues aspartic acid, glutamic acid, lysine, arginine, histidine which in their side chain groups contain ionic -COO^- or -NH_3^+ and imino groups so that these residues are highly hydrophilic in nature. All amino acids contain two additional ionic groups -COO^- and -NH_3^+ attached to α -carbon atom of the acid. In Figs. 2 to 4 the adsorption isotherms obtained from the plots of n_1 vs a_1 for nine amino acids respectively have been compared with each other at the range of water activities zero to unity. The shapes of these isotherms in Figs. 2 and 3 agree with type III BET isotherm¹⁸. In Fig. 4, isotherms are similar to type II BET isotherm¹⁸.

Fig. 1. (A) Amino acid (AA); Zwitterionic form, (B) polyamino acid (PAA residue), n = degree of polymerization.

Fig. 2. Plot of n_1 vs a_1 for (O) L-alanine, (□) L-arginine, (Δ) L-proline at 30 °C.

It has been previously explained^{16,20} that 20 different synthetic homo polypeptides (Fig. 1B) with n number of

Fig. 3. Plot of n_1 vs a_1 for (O) glycine, (□) L-lysine hydrochloride, (Δ) L-serine at 30 °C.

Fig. 4. Plot of n_1 vs a_1 for (O) L-isoleucine, (Δ) L-methionine, (□) L-tryptophan.

degree of polymerization undergo primary stage of hydration between a_1 equal to zero to 0.3 as a result of the formation of monolayer due to the water binding to hy-

drophilic groups present at the interface. Between 0.30 to 0.92 values of a_1 , more water molecules are adsorbed to the hydrophilic groups thus forming secondary layer of water on the polypeptide (pAA) interface. Values (n_1^s) of water molecules present in primary and secondary layers together are given per mole of residues in Table 1 at $a_1 = 0.92$. For non-polar residues¹⁶ values of n_1^s varies from 0.2 to 1.0 mole per mole of a residue while those for polar residues vary from 0.07 to 18 moles per mole. For ionic residues of polyamino acids, n_1^s varies between 4.6 to 12 moles per mole of residue as expected^{16,20}.

When a_1 exceeds 0.92, n_1 for an amino acid residue (vide Table 1) sharply increases due to the formation of multilayers of water molecules upto a_1 equal to unity. The multilayers of water are termed as tertiary layers of hydrated amino acid residue¹⁶. Total amounts of water (equal to Δn_1^0) associated per mole of amino acid residue have been evaluated from the extrapolation of the values of n_1 to $a_1 \rightarrow 1$. Δn_1^0 has earlier been found to vary from 1 to 74 moles per mole of amino residue present in polypeptide chain depending upon their chemical composition and the type of the side-chain groups in the chain^{16,20}.

In the present investigation, all the amino acid (AA) molecules contain NH_3^+ and COO^- groups attached to each α -carbon atoms in zwitter-ionic states. Further R and H groups are also attached to α -carbon atoms. Because of the presence of these charged COO^- and NH_3^+ groups, the hydration of monomeric amino acid (vide Fig. 1A) is expected to be always larger than those of corresponding uncharged amino acid residues (vide Fig. 1B) existing in the polypeptide chain. Comparison of values of n_1^s for amino acids in Table 1 (except proline) are found to be considerably lower than those of their corresponding residues which are not to be expected on structural grounds.

The powdered particles of an amino acid molecule containing hydrophobic side-chain is larger inside so that the specific surface area of its exposed surface is small. Number of water binding sites on the exposed surface area must be small compared to the total water binding sites of its crystal unit present in the particle. Further, large number of amino acid molecules hidden inside the solid particles are present in the form of ionic crystals^{21,22}. The melting temperatures²³ (vide Table 1) of dipolar amino acids containing side chain hydrophobic groups are much higher than other molecules of similar size. The crystal lattice of these amino acids is held together by strong

electro-static forces between NH_3^+ and COO^- groups of neighbouring molecules resulting in the formation of stable ionic crystals similar to NaCl ^{21,22}. Relatively high temperature is to be applied to such ionic lattice to separate strongly interacting positive and negative charge from each other causing melting of crystal. At ordinary temperature, the water molecules in the vapour state cannot penetrate the ionic crystal when p/p_0 is only 0.92 so that n_1^s value will be low.

On the otherhand, when amino acid residue occurs as part of linear polypeptide chain, NH_2 and COOH groups in α -carbon atom become part of peptide bond (Fig. 1B) so that its dipolar action disappears (except at the end groups). The powdered particles of peptide formed by residues remaining in the inside and outside surfaces of the particles are soft and non-crystalline in nature and water molecules may penetrate easily the surface and bind all available sites of the side-chains hidden inside the particle. Water binding capacity¹⁶ of $-\text{NHCO}-$ group is known to be negligible. This picture is valid also for hydration of globular and denatured proteins²⁰. This is the main reason that n_1^s for AA is much lower than that of PAA.

In Table 1, n_1^s for proline is much higher than that of polyproline because of the presence of pyrrolidyl groups in place of NH_3^+ group, the ionic crystal formed becomes weak as evidenced from considerable lowering of its melting temperature (vide Table 1) so that water molecules penetrate the crystal and bind to ionic groups of COO^- and pyrrolidyl group. Presence of hydrophilic groups in the side chain of the amino acid also lowers the strength of the ionic crystal so that in the case of serine, asparagine and lysine also n_1^s for AA is higher than those of respective PAA.

At p/p_0 tending to unity, each amino acid crystal begins to dissolve in water phase following a specific mechanism. Differences in the values of Δn_1^0 for AA and AAP are possibly dependent on the specific mechanisms for dissolution of various amino acid crystals and polypeptides near p/p_0 equal to unity.

The standard free energy change ΔG_w^0 for the hydration of amino acid powders can be calculated using Bull's equation^{24,26},

$$\Delta G_w^0 = -RT \int_0^{a_1=1} \frac{n_1}{a_1} da_1 \quad (1)$$

Here ΔG_w^0 stands for the free energy change due to the water vapour adsorption per mole of amino acid when a_1

Table 1. Values of Δn_1^0 and ΔG_w^0 for hydration of 20 different L-amino acids and polyamino acid residues at 30 °C

L-Amino acids	n_1^s at $a_1 = 92$ moles H ₂ O per mole AA	n_1^s at $a_1 = 0.92$ moles H ₂ O per mole ¹⁶ PAA residue	Δn_1^0 moles H ₂ O per mole PAA	Δn_1^0 mole H ₂ O per mole PAA residue	$-\Delta G_w^0$ kJ per mole AA	Melting temp. of PAA (°C)
Non-polar R :						
Alanine	0.178	0.83	17.8	1.57	1.49	298
Valine	0.129	0.600	1.76	1.14	0.993	315
Leucine	0.099	0.475	0.328	1.47	0.514	295
Isoleucine	0.086	0.543	1.31	6.23	0.761	283
Proline	11.7	0.981	43.1	2.27	12.1	220
Phenylalanine	0.149	0.19	4.95	2.06	0.307	283
Tryptophan	0.347	0.512	1.04	2.79	1.39	293
Methionine	0.069	0.577	0.894	3.49	0.496	283
Polar R :						
Glycine	0.039	0.495	30.0	1.05	1.89	235
Serine	1.16	0.88	65.1	1.50	4.83	228
Threonine	0.123	2.22	9.52	20.2	0.984	230 ^a
Cystine	0.061	0.067	2.72	0.57	0.840	258 ^b
Tyrosine	0.235	1.06	1.18	1.42	0.484	295
Asparagine	1.10	0.406	3.43	9.36	0.857	2.36
Glutamine	0.175	18.4	10.2	59.00	1.51	205
Ionic R :						
Aspartic acid	0.296	11.0	0.931	56.2	0.896	270
Glutamic acid	0.088	11.9	0.788	26.4	0.824	247
Arginine HCl	30.1	9.61	128.0	73.7	31.5	244
Lysine HCl	3.58	4.62	73.7	32.8	12.4	238
Histidine HCl, H ₂ O	0.231	7.46	31.4	32.0	1.13	287

^aThreonine (dl), ^bcystine.

(or p/p_0) is brought from zero to its standard state unity. Plotting n_1/a_1 against various values of a_1 between the limits zero and unity, the graphical area for integration has been evaluated so that ΔG_w^0 for each amino acid can be calculated. These values for 20 different amino acids are also presented in Table 1.

One notes from this Table 1 that ΔG_w^0 for non-polar amino acid varies from 0.3 to 1.5 kJ per mole whereas those for polar amino acids, ΔG_w^0 varies from 0.48 to 1.90 kJ per mole depending on the nature of the side-chain groups. For amino acids having ionic side chains also, ΔG^0 for Asp, Glu and His varies from 0.9 to 1.1 kJ per mole. For lysine and arginine, ΔG^0 values are as high as 31.5 and 12.4 kJ per mole respectively possibly due to full ionization of the side-chain groups at pH at-

tained at isopiestic equilibrium.

In the derivation of eq. (1) by Bull²⁴, biopolymer-water system in the hydration process has been assumed to contain two steps occurring in a single phase system. Bryan²⁵ has assumed the existence of four steps in the hydration process but his treatment finally leads to the same expression for the hydration process. It has also been shown²⁶ that eq. (1) can be derived if biopolymer-water mixture in the sample is assumed to remain as two phase system.

In our isopiestic experiments, with powdered amino acids, we have already noted that the value of n_1 is low at a_1 less than 0.92 for all amino acids. With the increase of a_1 , n_1 is observed to increase sharply for lysine HCl at a_1 equal to 0.985 and glycine, threonine at a_1 equal to 0.85

and proline and serine at a_1 near 0.92. These amino acids are apparently found to be soluble completely in the sample bottle at these values of water activities respectively and values of Δn_1^0 for $a \rightarrow 1$ are large. For remaining amino acids, Δn_1^0 values are relatively small when a_1 is close to unity. At a_1 equal to unity all amino acids should be soluble in water but the concentrations of the acids at saturation points are widely different from each other (vide Table 2).

We shall assume that powdered amino acids in contact with adsorbed water between a_1 equal to zero and 1 form single phase hydrogel except lysine, glycine, threonine, asparagine, proline, serine (and few other amino

Table 2. Activity coefficient of amino acid in gel at a_1 equal to 0.995 at 30 °C

Sample	m_2^{sat}	f_2	pH
Phe	0.174	0.215	5.28
Trp	0.7	0.534	5.23
Leu	0.175	0.213	6.03
Heu	0.281	0.133	5.65
Val	0.518	0.072	5.71
Glu	0.06	0.624	2.96
Asp	0.057	0.657	4.10
Asn	0.255	0.147	4.57
Gln	0.328	0.114	5.75
Met	0.226	0.110	5.43

acids) which are observed to be completely soluble in adsorbed water below a_1 less than unity. These are also forming single phase binary solution of water and amino acid.

With reference to the solute activity unity, the activity coefficient f_2 of an amino acid in the isopiestic vapour pressure measurement at a given water activity a_1 close to unity can be calculated using eq. (2),

$$\ln f_2 = - \int_0^1 \frac{X_2}{X_1} d \ln a_1 \quad (2)$$

derived on thermodynamic grounds²⁴. It is however, assumed here that all amino acids are zwitterionic at an isoionic pH and they behave as a non-electrolyte. Here X_1 and X_2 stand for mole fractions of water and AA. Using graphical plot of X_2/X_1 against a_1 between the limits zero to a_1 equal to 0.985, 0.990, 0.995, values of f_2 for different amino acids have been evaluated using eq. (2). Values of f_2 for a_1 equal to 0.995 have been pre-

sented in Table 2 for several amino acids of low solubilities. From the known values of amounts of H_2O and AA in the mixture present in the sample bottle, values of X_1 and X_2 can be calculated. The solubilities of the amino acids presented in Table 2 in the state of saturation have been presented in separate experiments at water activity unity using Folin reagent²⁸. At $a_1 = 0.995$, values of f_2 however widely varies from 0.072 for Val to 0.657 for Asp since the deviation of different amino acids from ideal behaviour is different in aqueous medium.

Materials and methods :

Twenty different L-amino acids from Sigma Co., USA were used in the present isopiestic vapour pressure experiment. The names, sample numbers and abbreviations of the amino acids are following : alanine A 7627 (Ala); valine V 0500 (Val); leucine L 8000 (Leu); isoleucine I 2752 (Ilu); proline P 0380 (Pro); phenylalanine P 2126 (Phe); tryptophan T 0254 (Trp); methionine M 9625 (Met); glycine G 7126 (Gly); serine S 4500 (Ser); threonine T 8625 (Thr); cystine C 8755 (Cys); tyr T 3754 (Tyr); asparagine A 0884 (Asn); glutamine G 3126 (Gln); aspartic acid A 9256 (Asp); glutamic acid G 1251 (Glu); lysine HCl L 5626 (Lys); arginine HCl A 5131 (Arg); histidine HCl H 8125 (His). All amino acids were reported to be extremely pure by TLC assay (99 percent purity). A.R. grade sulphuric acid from E. Merck, India was used. Double distilled water was used throughout the investigation.

Bull and co-workers^{16,20,24} earlier developed the isopiestic vapour pressure method for the quantitative measurement of hydration of proteins. The method has been used by Chattoraj and co-workers^{17,20} for the study of hydration of powdered proteins²⁵⁻²⁷. In the present study also, the same isopiestic method was used for the study of hydration of 20 L-amino acids in the range of water activity zero to unity. Before use, all the amino acids were dried completely by keeping them in a vacuum desiccator, containing concentrated H_2SO_4 .

For the study of hydration of an amino acid in the absence of a neutral solute, a definite weight (W_1) of dry amino acid was taken in a previously weighed specially designed weighing bottle. The lid of weighing bottle was taken out and the bottle containing the powdered sample was allowed to float on 100 ml H_2SO_4 solution in the desiccator. The concentration of H_2SO_4 was varied from 0.50 (N) to 29.0 (N) and these are referred to as "reference solution". The desiccator was closed, evacuated ap-

appropriately, and kept in an air-thermostat for several days at a fixed temperature. The accuracy of the temperature maintained in the thermostat was within 0.1 °C. The free exchange of water vapour occurred between the sample bottle containing powdered acid and magnetically stirred reference solution. Approximately after five days, isopiestic equilibrium was attained. The desiccator was then opened carefully and weight of the weighing bottle closed with lid was noted after washing the outside surface with distilled water, followed by gentle drying with filter paper. From the initial weight W_i and final W_f of sample bottle all expressed in gram, moles (n_1) of water vapour adsorbed per kilogram of dry L-amino acid was calculated using equation,

$$n_1 = \left(\frac{W_f - W_i}{W_i} \right) \times \frac{1000}{18} \quad (3)$$

The concentration of H_2SO_4 in the reference solution at equilibrium was estimated titrimetrically and the corresponding value of relative humidity (p/p^0) was obtained from the standard table^{20,21,24}. The standard deviation of measurement of n_1 was found not to exceed 3 percent. From Raoult's law, p/p_0 is equal to water activity a_1 for the system.

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